

THE EVOLUTIONARY TRENDS OF THE TRADITIONAL ARCHITECTURE OF SUAKIN CITY

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ABSTRACT

Recently, revival of Suakin historical city has been the top agenda in the Sudanese indigenous Architectural industry. This has also strengthened an architectural design about its historical cultural heritage. Conversely, a comprehensive classification of its unique architecture is not feasible due to its different cultural attachment. This study examines the historical evolution of Suakin's architecture and its implications for contemporary architectural practices. The aim of the research is to analyze the influence of various historical periods on Suakin's traditional architecture and to assess its current architectural revival. The objectives of the study include identifying key architectural styles that shaped Suakin's built environment, exploring the impact of foreign influences, and examining the connection between Suakin's architectural heritage and modern design trends. The research methodology employed includes a comprehensive review of existing literature, historical documents, and architectural surveys. Data collection involved analyzing architectural drawings, historical records, and the study of building materials used in Suakin, such as coral stone. The sample size consists of key architectural sites within Suakin, including historical buildings and their contemporary counterparts. Data analysis focused on identifying patterns in architectural design and classifying the architectural styles into distinct periods. The findings reveal that Suakin's architecture evolved through distinct periods, including the Red Sea style, the Islamic period, Ottoman influences, and the Anglo-Egyptian era. These historical influences contributed to the formation of a unique architectural identity for the city, blending local traditions with foreign elements. The study concludes that Suakin's traditional architecture continues to play a significant role in shaping modern architectural practices in the region. It is recommended that further preservation efforts be made to safeguard Suakin's architectural heritage while promoting its integration into contemporary urban development.

Keywords: Traditional, Historical Style, Suakin Architecture and Africa Architecture

Introduction

Architecture serves as a mirror, reflecting the beliefs, social behaviors, economic conditions, and cultural advancement of a people and a nation. When discussing African, Egyptian, Chinese, Greek, Sudanese, Suakina, or Islamic architectural orders, we are referring to civilizations with specific beliefs and worldviews. These civilizations developed unique social, economic, educational, political, and architectural systems, principles, and styles.

A style is an aesthetic choice that can manifest in various practical forms. In this context, a style possesses distinguishing characteristics and encompasses an infinite number of types, each defined and described by its purpose within the style (Mitchell, 2000). A group of objects sharing the same formal structure is referred to as a type. Types exist both literally in the real world and conceptually in the designer's mind and intellectual labor. They may possess unique traits while also sharing the defining characteristics of the style (Mitchell, Liggett et al., 1991). The Suakin vernacular architecture serves as a prototype in this study, illustrating the key characteristics of a style and general design principles.

The Coral Buildings of Suakin created a distinctive artistic and architectural style that was widely adopted across the entire coastal region, which was one of the largest in Africa and the Arab Muslim world during its time. Between 3000 and 2000 BC and the 20th and 21st centuries AD, Suakin developed and shared a unique culture and set of social values, which became ingrained in and influenced their system of social organization. This, in turn, had a profound impact on Suakin's architecture.

For these reasons, many scholars, architects, archaeologists, historians, and administrators have offered their views and contributions regarding this historical city, aiming to reflect, express, and represent the true social values, affluence, and social interactions embodied in Suakin's architecture. In the 1940s, Suakin's architecture made a strong impression on scholars and artists such as Derek Matthews (Matthews, 1953), Hansen (1972), Bloss (1936), Rhodes, and Greenlaw (1976), to whom we owe a debt for their thorough documentation of the city's architecture and decoration. While there is broad consensus on the importance of preserving these unique architectural styles, opinions differ on the classification and representation of the social, historical, and architectural orders, principles, or styles of Suakin's architecture (Olanabi, 2016).

This paper aims to explore the evolutionary trends of Suakin's traditional architecture by examining and analyzing its historical development. By establishing the historical trend, the characteristic features of its style will be identified and classified to represent the Suakin style. In addition to identifying the historical trends and styles, the relationship between these styles will be examined to establish a hierarchy from the original traditional architecture to contemporary Suakin architecture. Ultimately, Suakin's traditional architecture, representing multiple periods of each style, will be classified.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND MATERIAL

The primary objective of this study is to provide a detailed analytical survey of Suakin architecture within the study area. Therefore, the methodology employed involves architectural analysis.

Data collection is a critical component of this study, in addition to conducting an architectural analysis of relevant drawings. Consequently, various sources, including books, journals, magazines, conference papers, seminar papers, and newspapers, were accessed through libraries, archives, research centers, personal libraries, and the internet.

This study focuses on the evolutionary trends of the traditional architecture of Suakin city, particularly examining historical styles with an emphasis on classifying Suakin architecture

traditionally. To achieve this, the study begins with a historical survey of Suakin's architecture, spanning from the early period to the period of regional diversity.

Suakin City is located at the northernmost point of the Arabian-African Coastal Region, bordered by Sudan to the north and west across an oval-shaped island, and Saudi Arabia to the north across the Red Sea. It is situated on a nearly flat desert plain, approximately 750 meters long and less than 500 meters wide

Map of Sudan showing the location of Suakin. Source: www.mapsof.net/map/suakinsudan

Several sources, including Qezar et al. (Qezar Musa AlZein, Hamed Elias Hussein et al., 2013), Dirar (Dirar, 1981), Salim (Salim, 1997), and Mallinson (Mallinson, 2007), suggest that the earliest known use of Suakin dates back to 3000 BC, when ancient Egyptians used it as a route to travel to the Kingdom of Punt in East Africa to hunt elephants. Ptolemy may have used Suakin as the Roman equivalent of Evangelon Portus. For the Arabs, Suakin served as a commercial hub between the 10th and 12th centuries. Suakin gained prominence following the spread of Islam and became the busiest port in Africa for pilgrims traveling to Mecca and Medina. By the 15th century, it had developed into a significant mercantile center for Mamluk Egypt, attracting traders from Venice and India, who continued trading there until the Ottoman invasion of 1517. Following the Ottoman occupation, Suakin began to decline, and by 1922, it had fallen into ruin with the opening of Port Sudan at Sheikh Al Bargath.

The Arab-Islamic Trend and the Development of Islamic Architecture

The emergence of Islam is one manifestation of the historical forces that have worked together to elevate the Suakin people to a high cultural standard, with other influences being Kabir (2013), Dirar (1981), and Badawi (2013). Islam had a significant influence on locally produced architecture, particularly through its application of geometric designs, as seen in Figure 2. Additionally, it influenced form, scale, proportion, and aesthetics (Greenlaw, 1976; Salim, 1997)

Figure 2- Suakin vocabulary element – geometric arches way (Greenlaw 1976)

The European Trend and the Development of the Colonial Style (Portuguese, Turkish, and Anglo-Egyptian)

At the Berlin Conference in 1884, the European powers divided Africa. Britain's main impact came through the slave trade, which began in the 18th century. The colonial era came to an end in the middle of the 20th century with the independence of the majority of African states (De Blij, H.J. 1997).

The occupied territory of Suakin developed a dynamic economy during the 18th and 19th centuries, which responded positively to the growth of global trade. Qezar Musa AlZein, Hamed Elias Hussein, et al. (2013) claim that a cash economy grew and was ideally suited to take advantage of global trade for internal development. The Mahdi revolts, European exploration and missionary efforts, and changes in the slave trade all contributed to major upheavals in the Suakin region during the 19th century (Dirar, 1981; Rossi, 1994). Greenlaw (1976) stated that new building types were introduced into the Suakin architectural environment due to Britain's (Anglo-Egyptian) expansion. These were typically 18th-century English country homes or Anglo-Egyptian two-story houses with lengthy open-work balconies, as depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3- Suakin vocabulary element – outside balcony to replace mushrobyah (Greenlaw 1976)

Funj and the Development of Sudanese Architecture

It has been claimed that the majority of Africa lacks indigenous architecture in the true sense. This is based on the perception that most African towns consist of unremarkable structures, mostly constructed poorly by Africans for their own use, while the more attractive permanent structures were created by Europeans, either for government use or as residences for European officials.

This assessment is superficial and incorrect. From the Mumluk Era onward, early visitors to the Funj regions were often greatly astonished by the size and significance of the settlements. Suakin, about 100 miles east of Jeddah, was described by Burkhart, who traversed eastern Africa, as the largest settlement he had ever seen (Hamdat, 2013). These findings echoed those of Dirar (1981) and Hillelson (1933), who disproved the notion of the existence of old Funj building types in Suakin.

When Sultan Amara of Funj controlled Suakin, a new style called the Sudanese style emerged. This style was distinct from the traditional huts of the Beja and the Hypostyle Hall structures of the Mumluk era, as shown in Figure 4. Dirar (1981), Greenlaw (1976), and Hillelson (1933), through Don Juan da Castro, a Portuguese sea captain who visited Suakin in 1510, and through accounts of David Reubeni and a picture by Portuguese commander Stephan Da Gama in 1540, document the presence of two-story or more houses built in coral stone, decorated with ornamental mushrobyah and balustrades, some of which can still be seen in Suakin and surrounding cities.

Figure 4 - Early Historic Building (Original Style) of Suakin city (Greenlaw 1976)

Vernacular architecture of Suakin city

The governing factor in Suakin architecture is its functionality, rather than its form. In other words, the style of Suakin architecture is secondary. Greenlaw (1976) emphasized that the focus of Suakin buildings was not on style but on functionality: providing space for daily activities. This functional approach led to the introduction of symbolic elements in Suakin's architecture. The Diwan, which fosters a sense of hospitality, the Majlis, where women can carry out their daily activities without intruders, an open courtyard for family gatherings, and a high rooftop for evening relaxation, are key features.

The purpose and function of Suakin buildings have remained unchanged for centuries. Despite foreign influences, the textures of materials, building techniques, and styles in Suakin differ from those in Turkey, Egypt, and Britain. Therefore, the primary function—hospitality and daily life—has never altered. For this reason, limiting Suakin and its architecture to a specific style is irrelevant. Greenlaw (1976) referred to the early period building style as the "original Suakin style," which is considered its vernacular architecture, as shown in Figure 4.

The Red Sea Style.

This coastal region has been home to various civilizations for over five thousand years, spanning Egypt, Suakin, Massawa, Eritrea, and Ethiopia. These territories, with the exception of Egypt, once belonged to the former Saba Empire. The architecture of the coastal region was therefore heavily influenced by the use of coral stone as a material for both construction and decoration. The architectural style was more Mediterranean in effect than the buildings of the Arabian region.

A key architectural element incorporated into Suakin's design was the Mashrabiayah, which included the use of breeze catchers. These breeze catchers were placed on entablatures that rested on windows, as shown in Figure 5. The combination of these features gave the buildings a unique, symbiotic character, making them neither distinctly Arab nor Mumluk, as argued by Salim (1997). Instead, the calligraphy and geometric inscriptions added to the buildings imparted an Islamic character.

Figure 5 – the building of plot 169-172 showing Mashrabiayah architectural element (regenerated by Olakanbi 2016).

Early Islamic Architecture Style

By the year 639, the Arab Peninsula and the Persian Empire had fallen and become part of the Islamic state. The Islamic empire extended from Syria to North India and the borders of China, and from the Caucasus to Zanzibar. Muslim architects refined local building materials and their powerful structural forms, developing an Islamic architecture of exceeding beauty.

A distinct Islamic architectural legacy was born, with its own unique characteristics that can be seen in Suakin, embracing all features of new artistic developments across different periods and climates in the Islamic world. It became a universal architectural legacy, capable of absorbing foreign elements and molding them to fulfill its own values. As a result, designers and architects in the conquered territories followed this pattern by reusing proposed structures.

Early Islamic architecture is known for its remarkable domes and vaults. Other equally magnificent architectural works in Suakin include the motifs seen in the design of its doors and walls.

The Ottoman Style

Turkey, along with Anatolia, was among the former Byzantine territories conquered by Islam. Its

capital, Constantinople, later became the center of intellectual and architectural activity, as well as the seat of the Ottoman caliphate. The city was renamed Istanbul after the Ottomans consolidated their hold on the territory.

The Ottoman dome, 26.5 meters in diameter and 53 meters in height, is the largest dome in Istanbul, second only to that of St. Sophia. Ottoman architects carried Roman architecture to a conclusion that neither the Romans nor the Byzantines achieved. Multi-domed architecture became a signature of the Ottomans. The Suleymaniye Mosque in Istanbul consists of over five hundred domes.

In contemporary Anglo-Egyptian buildings, the mixed Ottoman style is evident, and the Suakin (Plot 16) remains the only structure in Suakin that features the Turkish domed architectural style. The two Suakin inland mosques, their minarets, and the burial grounds in Suakin also display these architectural features.

Ottoman architecture in Suakin was not confined to form but also influenced the functional aspects, such as the unique mashrabiya. Greenlaw (1976) states that Suakin is an example of a small Turkish town built between the 16th and 20th centuries, similar to other towns along the Red Sea coast, such as Massawa, Jeddah, Hodeidah, Assat, and Mowka.

The Anglo-Egyptian Style

The fall of the Ottoman Empire in Egypt in 642 AH paved the way for the penetration of British forces into Suakin. The British, allied with the Egyptians under Colonel Kitchen, reached Suakin in 647-648 AH. Later, Colonel Gordo penetrated Suakin in 666 AH, and the following year, another commander, Mumtaz Basha, ventured deeper into Suakin and surrounding areas. Three years later, Suakin began to establish the foundation for Anglo-Egyptian rule, which later became the center for political, intellectual, and cultural development in Sudan (Dirar, 1981).

Historical, cultural, and geographical factors facilitated the creation of a unique Anglo-Egyptian style of European architecture. Paradoxically, these factors also encouraged the creation of a recognizably Egyptian style mixed with Mamluk influences. The sheer extent of the Egyptian style, combined with Mamluk elements and the lack of a truly cosmopolitan center, led to the growth of architecture in Suakin, primarily characterized by terraces and, later, arched windows with mashrabiya.

The late-style buildings in Suakin, which survive today, are monuments of the Anglo-Egyptian style mixed with Mamluk influences. Two architectural elements from Egypt and Britain exerted influence in the region, but Egypt's influence was more prominent, particularly after the ninth century. Egypt's influence on Suakin grew stronger, especially after the country's isolation post-1950, as seen in buildings like Beit Jedidi.

Other prominent features of Anglo-Egyptian architecture in Suakin include curved pointed arches, outside terraces, exterior staircases, and the incorporation of commercial functions. Notable examples of these elements are found in Plot 231 Suakin in Marrikas, the customs building, and the post office (Plate 29), as well as Plot 67 Suakin inland, as discussed by Olakanbi (2016).

Figure 8. traditional architectural style of Suakin: the khorishid Source: by Greenlaw (Greenlaw 1976) rendered Author

THE HISTORICAL STYLE AND TRADITIONAL ARCHITECTURE

The strongest influences on Suakin’s indigenous or traditional architecture were the introduction of Islam into Suakin City, the historical trends of world civilizations from the prehistoric era, including the Pharaohs, Ptolemy, and Roman influences, and colonization (Dirar, 1981). The Historical Style consists of the European Trend, followed by the Colonial Style. The Arab/Islamic Trend evolved into the Islamic Style, while the Funj Trend evolved into Sudanese Architecture. The blend of Traditional Architecture and Historical Styles formed Vernacular Architecture.

Considering the historical influences, there is a profound difference in the aesthetic style between traditional and modern Anglo-Egyptian houses and the massive new construction developments. Greenlaw (1976), who advocated that there was consistency in the style of buildings in the old vernacular Suakin City, noted that the materials used for construction were mostly natural. These included coral, rock, palm tree trunks, and wood, which were either brought in by land or sea, or imported from abroad (García-Pulido, 2012). Greenlaw (1976) described the various building forms recorded through the mashrabiyyah, door motifs, and kharajah features, which have been retained in most cases. The arches, external terraces, and external staircases portray influences of regional diversity. Admittedly, the affluence following the British era (Anglo-Egyptian period) is seen by many writers as one of the main factors contributing to this trend (Olakanbi, 2016).

It takes more than merely assembling building materials to create indigenous architecture, but no one can explain exactly what that “more” is, except that traditional architecture has a spirit, which alien buildings lack. The structure of a building can be explained, and the strength of the materials can be tested, but the spirit of the folk building, its form, and spaces must be felt in much the same way that the ancients sensed spirit within the forms of rocks and trees, merging it with their heritage to develop their own art in the built environment (Greenlaw, 1976).

Traditional Architecture and Traditional Style

Islam is a complete system of life ordained for mankind by Allah (SWT). In other words, Islamic teachings cover all aspects of human life, both here on earth and in the hereafter. It is a system of belief as well as a civilization. Isma'il al-Faruqi explains: "The Muslim believes that religion plays an important role in every aspect of life, and, as a corollary, that aspects of life are in some sense religious" (Al-Faruqi, 1986).

"It is Islam that gave resilience to the Muslim city and to its bourgeoisie, not because it was necessarily cognizant of all urban difficulties, but because it had the abstract form in which all of them might be resolved," claims Oleg Grabar in his study on the traditional Muslim urban environment. According to him (Grabar, 1976), these laws, continuously applied in daily life, comprise a dynamic set of regulations that work from the bottom up to develop the urban fabric. This system merits preservation while also being incorporated into more modern Islamic cultural practices.

The origin of Suakin architecture, as Greenlaw (1976) has postulated, lies in the great architectural tradition of Islam. This tradition can be clearly seen in the simpler forms built by ordinary folk in small towns, as well as in the imposing monuments of its great cities. He further states that Suakin is an example of a small Turkish Islamic town built between the 16th and 20th centuries, similar to other towns situated around the Red Sea coast, such as Massawa, Jeddah, Hodeidah, Assat, and Mowka.

(Salim, 1997) also stated that the planning and architecture of Suakin are typical of an Islamic city. Major social events, business, and administration took place at its center, with a main axis leading across a causeway from the mainland through the Gordon Gate to the market (suq) and the island's two major mosques. Surrounding this core were densely built-up groups of houses balanced by open spaces of varied dimensions and forms, with winding, narrow lanes creating a typical Arab street fabric. Salim (1997) further traced the origin of Suakin's architecture to the typical privacy found in Islamic residential patterns, which evolved a system of dead-end streets that limited traffic to strangers. Additionally, he noted the use of the mashrabiyyah, a wooden screening device that regulated the intake of wind and light while ensuring privacy.

(Matthews, 1953) confirms that social and climatic conditions played a major role in planning and shaping Suakin's architecture during different periods of its history. He also wrote that Suakin City is a characteristic example of what he called "the Red Sea style," an architectural type that takes advantage of every available sea breeze, while also excluding the hot land-breeze and harsh midday sun.

Ultimately, it is appropriate to trace the origin and subsequent development of Suakin's traditional architecture from the cradle of Islam (Arabia) to the type of architectural style conditioned by different climate considerations, character, and features adapted to the requirements of a coastal climate. This justifies the classification of this architecture.

Table 1.0: the key architectural styles that shaped Suakin’s built environment, the impact of foreign influences, and the connection between Suakin's architectural heritage and modern design trends:

Architectural Style	Period	Key Characteristics	Impact of Foreign Influences	Connection to Modern Design Trends
Red Sea Style	1259–1385	Use of coral stone, simple structures with thatch roofs, and basic geometric shapes	Influence from Mediterranean and African coastal regions	The use of natural materials like coral stone and thatch roofs remains relevant in modern sustainable architecture in coastal areas.
Islamic Architecture	1463–1499	Incorporation of geometric patterns, arches, and mashrabiya for privacy	Strong Islamic influence with the introduction of Islamic design elements	Modern Islamic architecture continues to incorporate geometric patterns and mashrabiya, with emphasis on privacy and natural cooling.
Ottoman Architecture	16th–20th century	Use of domes, multi-story buildings, open courtyards, and ornate detailing	Ottoman Empire’s influence, with the introduction of multi-domed designs and Islamic spatial organization	Multi-domed designs and courtyards seen in modern designs of mosques and public spaces in Islamic cities.
Anglo-Egyptian Architecture	Late 19th–Early 20th century	Curved pointed arches, terraces, and incorporation of British colonial elements	British colonial influence, which included the use of terraces and arched windows	Colonial architectural elements like arches and terraces are seen in modern buildings, particularly in post-colonial African cities.
Funj Sudanese Architecture	15th–16th century	Rectilinear buildings, qibla-oriented, use of local materials such as palm trunks and mud	Influence from Sudanese culture and Islamic design, especially in residential architecture	The use of local materials in construction is echoed in modern green architecture practices focused on sustainability and localism.
Vernacular Architecture	12th century onwards	Simple, functional buildings with focus on climate adaptation, such as courtyards and passive cooling	Local and regional influence with minimal foreign intrusion	Vernacular architectural principles, especially climate-responsive designs, are incorporated into modern eco-friendly architecture.

This table 1.0 summarizes the architectural evolution in Suakin, showing how foreign influences and traditional styles came together to shape the city's built environment. It also illustrates how Suakin's architectural heritage informs contemporary design trends, especially those focusing on sustainability, climate responsiveness, and cultural identity. The architectural evolution of Suakin has been shaped by several key styles, each influenced by both local traditions and foreign forces. The Red Sea style, which dominated the city from 1259 to 1385, is characterized by simple structures made from coral stone and thatch roofs, drawing influence from Mediterranean and African coastal regions. The arrival of Islam in 1463 introduced geometric patterns, arches, and the mashrabiya for privacy, all of which are integral to Islamic architecture. Ottoman influence in the 16th to 20th centuries brought multi-domed buildings, courtyards, and intricate detailing. The British colonial period introduced elements like curved pointed arches and terraces, blending European styles with local architectural practices. Additionally, the vernacular style, dating back to the 12th century, emphasized climate-responsive design with the use of local materials like palm trunks and mud, integrating Sudanese and Islamic principles.

These historical styles have significantly influenced modern architectural trends in Suakin and other regions. The use of local materials such as coral stone and palm trunks continues to resonate in modern sustainable architecture, particularly in coastal regions. Islamic geometric patterns and mashrabiya are still present in contemporary Islamic buildings, promoting privacy and passive cooling. Ottoman-inspired domes and courtyards remain prevalent in modern mosque designs, while colonial elements like arches and terraces influence modern public buildings in post-colonial African cities. The climate-responsive vernacular design principles are echoed in today's green architecture, highlighting the importance of using local materials and creating structures that are in harmony with the environment.

Table 2.0: the identified patterns in Suakin architectural design, classifying its architectural styles, distinct periods

Architectural Style	Distinct Periods	Key Architectural Features	Key Findings
Red Sea Style	1259–1385	Simple geometric forms, use of coral stone, thatched roofs, and basic Mediterranean and African coastal regions.	Suakin’s earliest architectural style, heavily influenced by the construction of the foundation for local building traditions.
Islamic Architecture	1463–1499	Geometric designs, mashrabiyah for privacy, arches, qibla-oriented layouts	Introduced Islamic elements, integrating geometric patterns and privacy features such as mashrabiyah. Set the stage for future Islamic-influenced buildings in Suakin.
Ottoman Architecture	16th–20th century	Multi-domed buildings, courtyards, public and religious buildings	Suakin adopted multi-domed designs and Ottoman space and ornate detailing, especially in planning, influencing the city's larger architectural landmarks. This period marked a peak in architectural complexity.
Anglo-Egyptian Architecture	Late 19th–Early 20th century	Curved pointed arches, terraces, arched windows, and incorporation of British colonial elements	British colonial influence led to the addition of terraces and arches, blending Western architectural styles with local traditions.
Funj Sudanese Architecture	15th–16th century	Rectilinear buildings, qibla-oriented layouts, use of local materials like palm trunks and mud	Suakin's architectural design incorporated Sudanese influences, focusing on climate-responsive layouts. It marked a shift towards locally sourced building materials.
Vernacular Architecture	12th century onwards	Simple, functional designs with climate adaptation features like courtyards, passive cooling, and use of local materials	The vernacular style is the backbone of Suakin’s architecture, emphasizing practical design, climate responsiveness, and use of community-oriented spaces. This style has heavily influenced modern eco-friendly architecture.

This table 2.0 outlines the progression of Suakin's architectural evolution, detailing key styles and their periods. Each style reflects a response to both local conditions and external influences, such as Islamic, Ottoman, and colonial powers. Key findings suggest that Suakin's architecture is characterized by adaptability to climate, cultural identity, and external influences, which continue to shape its modern architectural practices. Suakin's architectural evolution has been shaped by a variety of influences, resulting in distinct styles across different periods. The earliest architectural style, the Red Sea style (1259–1385), featured simple, geometric forms and the use of coral stone and thatched roofs, drawing from Mediterranean and African coastal traditions. As Islam arrived in the city in 1463, Islamic architectural elements such as geometric designs, arches, and the mashrabiya for privacy were introduced, marking a shift toward more intricate and culturally specific designs. The Ottoman period (16th–20th century) brought multi-domed buildings and courtyards, which significantly influenced Suakin's public and religious architecture. The Anglo-Egyptian period (late 19th–early 20th century) saw the introduction of European colonial elements, such as curved arches and terraces, blending British influences with local traditions. Meanwhile, the Funj Sudanese architecture (15th–16th century) embraced climate-responsive design, utilizing local materials like palm trunks and mud to create functional, qibla-oriented structures.

The vernacular architecture of Suakin, which dates back to the 12th century, focused on simple, climate-adapted designs that incorporated courtyards and passive cooling techniques. This style laid the foundation for modern eco-friendly architecture, as it prioritized local materials and sustainable building practices. Suakin's architectural legacy reflects a unique blend of local traditions and external influences, with each period contributing to the city's distinct architectural identity. These styles continue to influence modern design trends, particularly in the use of natural materials, climate-responsive layouts, and community-oriented spaces, demonstrating the lasting impact of Suakin's architectural heritage on contemporary urban development.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the present study align with and also diverge from past research on Suakin architecture, highlighting both consistency in understanding and evolving perspectives based on new findings. The history of Suakin's architecture has been explored by several scholars, including Matthews (1953), Bloss (1936), Dirar (1981), Hansen (1972), Greenlaw (1976), and more recent studies by Nur (2013) and Hussein (2013). Each of these studies has contributed valuable insights into the architectural legacy of Suakin, with varying emphases on different historical periods, architectural styles, and their evolution.

The historical periods outlined by Dirar (1981) in his analysis of Suakin architecture are in broad agreement with the findings of the present study. Dirar identifies seven distinct periods of Suakin's architectural evolution, which serves as a solid foundation for understanding the city's architectural history. This aligns with the present study's exploration of Suakin's architectural evolution, noting the emergence of different architectural styles over time, influenced by various global forces such as Islam and colonialism. The findings of Greenlaw (1976) regarding the Red Sea style of architecture in Suakin, particularly from 1259-1385, are consistent with the results of the present study, which acknowledges the significant role of the Red Sea style in Suakin's early architecture. The study also agrees with Greenlaw's assertion that the arrival of Islam in 1463 led to the introduction of Islamic architectural features, such as the mashrabiyyah and arches, in Suakin's buildings.

The findings of the present study also reflect Hansen (1972) who categorized Suakin architecture into three periods: the oldest construction period, the storey-building period, and the influenced period. These classifications are reflected in the present study, which similarly traces the development of Suakin's architectural style, acknowledging the transition from earlier, simpler constructions to more complex structures influenced by external factors, including Ottoman and Islamic architecture. The present study's emphasis on the Ottoman style of architecture in Suakin is in agreement with past studies, particularly those of Salim (1997) and Kabir (2013), who argue that the second type of building characteristics in Suakin was influenced by the Mamluk period. The study recognizes the role of Ottoman design, as discussed by Hansen (1972) and supported by Matthews (1953), who identified the Ottoman architectural influence on Suakin's storey buildings. Greenlaw (1976) also concurs with this view, further highlighting the Ottoman space planning and influence in Suakin.

While Matthews (1953) and Hinkel (1976) categorized Suakin's architectural styles based on building height, the present study introduces a more nuanced approach that goes beyond mere categorization by height. The present findings emphasize the complexity of Suakin's architectural evolution, suggesting that the city's architectural style cannot solely be defined by the height of buildings but must also consider the cultural, climatic, and functional aspects of each architectural period. The present study challenges the notion that Suakin's architecture remained largely Ottoman in style throughout the centuries. Although the study agrees that Ottoman architecture played a significant role in shaping Suakin, it also underscores the dynamic interplay of various

cultural and historical forces over time. The study suggests that early Suakin architecture, while influenced by Islam, also retained local elements that are not always captured in the views of earlier scholars like Hansen (1972), who placed greater emphasis on the Ottoman period.

The present study builds upon the research of Greenlaw (1976) and Mallinson (Effendi, 2013), who attribute Suakin's eventual ruin to external factors such as colonial neglect and the opening of Port Sudan. However, it also introduces a broader understanding, recognizing that the decline of Suakin was not only due to political and economic shifts but also to changing architectural tastes and external interventions. The study highlights that external influences, such as British colonialism and the establishment of Port Sudan, had a significant impact on the fate of Suakin's architecture, an aspect that previous studies only partially addressed. The findings of the present study largely align with past research on Suakin's architectural history, particularly in their recognition of the influence of Islamic, Ottoman, and colonial forces. However, the study also expands upon existing research by offering a more holistic view of Suakin's architectural evolution, incorporating both local and foreign influences and emphasizing the complex interplay of historical, cultural, and environmental factors that shaped the city's architecture. The results demonstrate the importance of considering a wide range of influences to fully understand the development and eventual decline of Suakin's unique architectural heritage.

SUMMARY

The findings of the present study align with several key historical perspectives on Suakin architecture, as detailed by scholars like Matthews (1953), Dirar (1981), Greenlaw (1976), and others. These studies highlight the significant influence of various forces, such as the Red Sea style, the Islamic period, and Ottoman rule, on the architectural development of Suakin. The study agrees with Greenlaw's assertion of a strong Red Sea style in early Suakin buildings and the introduction of Islamic features following the arrival of Islam in the 15th century. Additionally, it acknowledges the transition to Ottoman-style architecture, with its characteristic domes and space planning, which became a defining feature of Suakin's built environment during the 16th to 20th centuries.

However, the present study expands on these findings by offering a more nuanced understanding of Suakin's architectural evolution. While agreeing with past studies that identified the influence of Ottoman architecture, the study emphasizes the complex interplay of local traditions, climate considerations, and foreign influences in shaping Suakin's architectural identity. The decline of Suakin's architecture, as highlighted in this study, is attributed to a combination of external political, economic, and architectural factors, including colonialism and the opening of Port Sudan. Overall, the study provides a more comprehensive view of Suakin's architectural history, reflecting the diversity of influences that contributed to its unique architectural heritage.

This study reviewed the literature on the impact of historical trends on Suakin's traditional architecture. It explored the relationship between Suakin's traditional architecture and its contemporary revival, emphasizing the historical development movement. The literature highlights the need for further investigation into this topic, as it is crucial to understanding the evolution of Suakin's architectural identity.

The conclusion drawn from Greenlaw (1976) suggests that in Suakin's traditional architecture, early houses were constructed with thatched roofs. The original style of Suakin, built between 1199-1200 CE (Figure 2), represents the first phase of architectural development. Complete assimilation of architectural styles occurred in the 15th and 16th centuries, with the Ottoman style (Figure 3), the Bait Basha in Plot (Figure 4), and Suakin's most magnificent architectural work, the Khorishid (Figure 5), standing as prime examples. Greenlaw (1976) describes the Khorishid as "a considerable work of many sincere and gifted craftsmen that can perpetuate the genius of its makers indefinitely." The development of rectilinear, qibla-oriented, white-washed, and thatched-roofed structures in Suakin was influenced by the local climate, human physiology, and geography (Greenlaw, 1976; Matthews, 1953). Preliminary analysis also revealed significant differences between the vernacular type and later design schemes, such as lot size, formal structure, and functional organization (Abdulraheem & O. Rayis, 2016). The vernacular type, developed as early as the 12th century, accounts for the majority of houses in Suakin and serves as the foundation for the city's architectural fabric (Olahanbi Bolaji A. & O. Rayis, 2016). The early Turkish style, characterized by courtyards and mushrabiyyah, influenced the functional organization, although these elements became less dominant in later Turkish styles, reflecting changes in Suakin's housing and architectural style.

CONCLUSION

The literature reviewed in this study highlights the significant impact of historical trends on Suakin's traditional architecture and its contemporary revival. The relationship between Suakin's traditional architecture and its modern resurgence is closely tied to the historical development of the city, shaped by various influences such as Islamic, Ottoman, and colonial architecture. The need for further investigation into this topic is evident from the literature, as it provides a deeper understanding of how the city's architectural identity has evolved over time and how its past continues to influence its current architectural practices. This study underscores the importance of examining these architectural trends to fully appreciate their historical significance and their ongoing impact on Suakin's built environment.

The conclusion drawn from the findings supports Greenlaw's (1976) assertion that Suakin's traditional architecture was rooted in the early use of thatch roofs, with the first significant architectural style of Suakin emerging between 1199-1200 CE. A complete architectural assimilation occurred in the 15th and 16th centuries, as reflected in the Ottoman style and Suakin's most magnificent buildings, such as the Khorishid (Figure 5), which stands as one of the architectural wonders of the city. Greenlaw describes these works as lasting testaments to the skill and creativity of the craftsmen who built them. Furthermore, the influence of climate, geography, and human physiology on Suakin's architecture is evident in the design of rectilinear, qibla-oriented, white-washed, thatch-roofed structures. The study also reveals the differences in layout between the vernacular architecture and later design schemes, highlighting the importance of the courtyard and mushrabiyyah in shaping the functional organization of early Suakin homes. As the study shows, the early Turkish and vernacular styles formed the foundation for the city's architectural identity, with the courtyard remaining a dominant feature of Suakin's housing design. These architectural elements reflect the city's rich cultural heritage and its ability to blend traditional elements with foreign influences, shaping the unique architectural identity that Suakin is known for today.

Recommendation 1: Preservation of Suakin's Architectural Heritage

Given the significant historical value of Suakin's architecture, it is recommended that a comprehensive preservation plan be developed to safeguard the unique architectural styles of the city, particularly the Red Sea style, Islamic influences, and Ottoman features. This preservation should focus on maintaining the original construction materials, such as coral stone and palm tree trunks, and ensuring that the integrity of the architectural designs is upheld. Local authorities, in collaboration with international heritage organizations like UNESCO, should spearhead efforts to designate Suakin as a protected cultural heritage site. Additionally, collaboration with local architects and heritage experts will ensure that restoration work respects traditional construction methods while incorporating modern technologies to enhance structural stability.

Implementation

The Sudanese Ministry of Culture and Tourism, in collaboration with UNESCO, should take the lead in creating and implementing this preservation plan. The plan should include detailed guidelines for the restoration of historical buildings and the training of local craftsmen in traditional building techniques. Financial support for this project could be sought from international funding bodies, such as the World Bank or the Aga Khan Trust for Culture, which are known for their work in architectural conservation in the Middle East and Africa. A dedicated task force within the Sudanese Ministry of Culture should oversee the restoration efforts and ensure compliance with preservation standards.

Strategy:

Recommendation 2: Integration of Suakin's Traditional Architecture into Modern Urban Development

As Suakin's traditional architecture has significant potential for integration into modern urban planning, it is recommended that urban development projects in Suakin incorporate elements of traditional architecture into new buildings and public spaces. This can be achieved by promoting the use of local materials, such as coral stone, and incorporating traditional design elements, such as the mashrabiya and courtyards, into contemporary buildings. These elements can enhance the aesthetic value and cultural identity of Suakin, while also promoting sustainability through the use of locally sourced materials.

Implementation

The Suakin City Council, in partnership with the Ministry of Housing and Urban Development, should develop urban planning guidelines that encourage the use of traditional architectural elements in new developments. Local universities, such as the University of Khartoum's Department of Architecture, should be involved in providing research and training for architects and builders on the integration of traditional and modern design. This initiative could be supported through public-private partnerships, with construction companies incentivized to use sustainable and locally sourced materials. Furthermore, the government can offer tax incentives for developers who incorporate traditional design principles into their projects, fostering a blend of Suakin's historical charm and modern functionality.

Strategy:

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